

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

COLD TOLERANCE

Spikelet sterility in winter rice

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Spikelet sterility appeared at epidemic levels in farmers' fields of the North Telangana Zone of Andhra Pradesh in winter 1983-84. Average minimum temperatures 20 d before flowering, from 26 Feb to 4 Mar 1984, were around 15 °C (range 13.7-16.8 °C). In 1983, temperatures averaged 21.3 °C during the corresponding period.

We screened 22 rice varieties sown in the 1983-84 winter season for spikelet sterility. Entries were planted in 10-m² plots at 10- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

Sterile and healthy spikelets on 10 randomly selected panicles in each plot were counted. Genotypic differences for spikelet sterility were significant.

Sterility and grain yield of 22 rice cultivars under low temperature, 26 Feb-4 Mar 1984.

Variety	Sterility (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
NLR26706	2.7	5.8
MTU 2400	5.6	5.8
WGL 47877	6.4	5.7
RNR29692	6.5	5.9
WGL 26358	6.7	5.5
WGL 48828	7.1	5.8
WGL 48684	7.4	5.3
WGL 33808	7.7	5.4
Pothana	8.5	5.9
Tella Hamsa	8.7	5.0
WGL 48001	8.8	5.1
WGL 6861	9.3	5.4
MTU6286	9.9	5.1
C73905	10.0	5.8
MTU6910	10.3	4.6
WGL 39966	10.4	5.7
IR50	12.3	6.0
RNR99181	12.8	5.9
WGL 44645	13.2	5.8
RNR99377	14.6	5.8
IR13525	17.0	5.4
WGL 33343	18.1	5.0

Sterility varied from 2.7 to 18%. The lowest was in NLR26706 and the highest in WGL 33343 (see table).

Varieties NLR26706, MTU2400,

RNR29692, and WGL 26358 recorded higher grain yields with low sterility and can be used in low temperature zones and in breeding programs. □

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DROUGHT TOLERANCE

Response of short-duration rice cultivars to drought stress

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Twenty early-maturing rice cultivars from different sources were evaluated during the 1985 and 1986 wet seasons (WS) (Jun-Oct) under upland rainfed conditions along with check DR92 (a released variety) in a randomized block design with three replications. Seeds were sown directly in 6.0-m² plots with a

spacing of 20 cm between rows and 10 cm within rows. Soil preparation, fertilization (60-60-40 kg NPK/ ha), and weeding were as in standard, well-managed plot trials.

Rainfall was normal during 1985 WS but erratic in 1986, with a 16-d drought spell. The maturity period of all cultivars was longer by 2 to 27 d in 1986 because of severe drought stress (see table). The long drought spell and the prolonged maturity period reduced grain yield 10-91%. A significant and positive correlation ($r = 0.727$) was obtained between maturity prolongation and yield reduction due to drought stress.

Performance of rice cultivars under drought stress. Bhubaneswar, India, 1985-86.

Cultivar	Days to maturity		Yield (t/ha)		
	1985	1986	1985	1986	Yield reduction (%)
DR83-1	91	104	2.7	1.5	45
DR83-2	91	104	2.7	1.3	52
OR165-93-15	89	104	2.4	0.3	88
ORKM6	94	110	2.3	0.8	65
DR83-16	98	110	2.1	0.8	62
OR165-97-15	90	112	2.1	0.2	91
IET7613	89	100	2.1	0.5	76
IET7566	89	105	2.0	0.7	65
DR83-3	90	109	2.0	0.5	75
OR165-86-12	90	113	2.0	0.4	80
ORKM4	91	105	1.9	0.6	69
IET7564	92	119	1.7	0.2	88
IET7617	102	116	1.4	0.6	58
IET7261	102	114	1.3	0.8	37
IET7635	104	118	1.3	0.5	62
IET7625	105	120	1.2	0.8	34
IET7633	114	116	1.0	0.9	10
IET7614	102	112	0.7	0.7	-
IET7911	102	112	0.2	0.2	-
DR92 (check)	91	102	2.6	1.2	54
CD (0.05)			0.3	0.2	